

Philatelic Nudges: The Impact of Traffic Safety Stamps on Public Awareness and Behavior

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential of postage stamps and related philatelic products to nudge public awareness and behavior, particularly in traffic safety. Traffic accident fatality data was analyzed before and after traffic safety stamp issues across various countries to identify potential effects, and a qualitative analysis of literature on the topic area was conducted. The study also explores alternative strategies that could replace stamps in conveying critical information as postal usage declines. While quantitative analysis shows no significant short-term effects on traffic fatality rates from the 'nudge' of postage stamps, qualitative research indicates the potential for long-term impacts on public awareness and safety norms. Discussions of the implications of these findings within the framework of nudge theory in public administration, and directions for future research and policy, conclude the paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traffic safety remains a critical global concern, with road traffic injuries being a leading cause of death worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2018). In response, governments and organizations have implemented various interventions to improve road safety, including public awareness campaigns. One unique approach in this realm is issuing traffic safety-themed postage stamps and related philatelic products.

Two primary research questions guide this study:

1. Can postage stamps and other philatelic-related products (including envelope covers, special cancellations, and other related materials) be effectively used by governments or other organizations through their national postal systems to engender public awareness and positive behaviors for specific topics, such as traffic safety?
2. In light of declining postal usage, what alternative strategies can replace stamps to convey critical information and help nudge behavior in public administration contexts?

These questions are explored within the framework of nudge theory, a concept in behavioral economics that proposes positive reinforcement and indirect suggestions to influence behavior and decision-making (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). Nudge theory has gained traction in public administration as a potentially cost-effective and non-coercive method of

promoting public welfare (John et al., 2011), and has been seen increasingly as an important aspect of the field of behavioral public administration.

Postage stamps serve as "banal nationalist symbols" that can effectively communicate state-sanctioned messages to the public (Raento & Brunn, 2005). In the context of traffic safety, stamps can serve as a vehicle for disseminating information and promoting safe behaviors. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of such stamp issues in reducing traffic fatalities and influencing public awareness and behavior. By combining quantitative analysis of fatality rates with qualitative insights from existing literature, we seek to provide a comprehensive understanding of the potential impact of traffic safety stamp campaigns.

From a public administration perspective, using postage stamps as a policy tool represents an innovative approach to governance and public engagement. This aligns with the New Public Service paradigm, which emphasizes the government's role in serving citizens and creating public value (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015). By leveraging existing infrastructure like postal systems, governments can achieve policy goals cost-effectively while fostering civic engagement. However, as Frederickson and colleagues (2018) pointed out, the effectiveness of such initiatives must be rigorously evaluated to ensure responsible use of public resources and to maintain public trust.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: NUDGE THEORY IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Nudge theory, introduced by Thaler and Sunstein (2008), suggests that subtle changes in how choices are presented can significantly influence decision-making. In public administration, nudges have been applied to various domains, including health, finance, and environmental policy (Benartzi et al., 2017). Nudge theory has been successfully used in multiple public policy domains, such as promoting energy conservation (Allcott, 2011) and increasing organ donation rates (Johnson & Goldstein, 2003).

Postage stamps, as everyday objects with wide circulation, can be viewed as potential nudges. (Raento & Brunn, 2005). In the context of traffic safety, stamps could nudge citizens towards safer behaviors by increasing awareness and activating social norms. Beyond nationalistic messaging (Brunn & Bell, 2023), the stamp may be used as a tool to influence behavior as an extrinsic controlled motivator (Bandhu et al., 2024), reminding people of penalties that may occur for negative actions or behaviors. As an example, the United States Postal Service has indicated that it engages in such messaging, as noted on a collector souvenir page, acknowledging its "policy of issuing stamps to focus attention on areas of major concern to this nation and other nations of the world" (USPS, 1972). Implicit in the focus of such attention is a need for awareness and action for the matters featured on stamps when they move beyond nationalistic messaging or memorials for historical figures into argumentation and activism. Regarding argumentation, a stamp may appeal to logic, character, or emotion.

In the context of public administration, nudge theory represents a shift from traditional command-and-control regulation towards more subtle forms of governance. This

approach aligns with "soft paternalism" in public policy, where governments aim to influence behavior without restricting freedom of choice (Sunstein, 2014). However, critics like Lodge and Wegrich (2016) argue that nudge-based interventions may lack democratic accountability and transparency. Consistent with the above and continuing with the USPS example, the USPS as an independent agency still acts under the auspices of the Executive Branch; it may issue stamps, but it is not always clear who is being represented by the message; this may yield some confusion and disagreement in the public, which then receives the message, processes it, and either acts on it or not. Therefore, public administrators must consider the ethical implications and potential unintended consequences of nudge strategies in traffic safety and other policy domains.

The diagram below in Figure 1 illustrates how the nudge theory informs government interventions, such as issuing traffic safety stamps. These stamps aim to increase public awareness and influence public behavior towards safer driving habits. While the stamps are not a direct enforcement tool, they serve as subtle nudges to promote traffic safety by embedding safety messages into everyday life. These messages may be general or specific and guide a viewer toward actions given general paths of argumentation. The effectiveness of these interventions depends on their ability to enhance awareness and gradually shift behaviors, which may contribute to reducing traffic accidents over time. Whether a stamp can impact outcomes depends on maintaining action toward an intended goal (Bandhu et al, 2024); outcomes may also depend on the subject matter, as well as the form of the message and type of argumentation employed, which ultimately contribute to the clarity of the direction given and whether the message may be acted upon.

Figure 1. Nudge Theory and Government Interventions in Traffic Safety

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Quantitative Data Collection

The study utilized a dataset comprising traffic fatality rates from 39 countries before and after the issuance of traffic safety stamps. The data included:

- Year 0: Fatality rates in the year of the stamp issue
- Year 1: Fatality rates one year after stamp issue

- Year 2: Fatality rates two years after stamp issue
- Data on traffic fatalities is from the World Health Organization. A spreadsheet was compiled, with data from 2000 to 2019, including the results for all stamp issues during that time frame along with corresponding decreases or increases in traffic fatalities in that country for the year of, year after, and 2 years after an issue release.

A list of traffic safety postage stamps was obtained from the American Topical Association, a leading aggregator for collectors of stamps in various themes. New stamps are entered into their database as they are issued, and members update the information regularly, so it is the most thorough global dataset for postage stamps. ATA Checklist 738: Transportation- Traffic Safety had 1,210 entries. Entries not related to traffic safety were removed from the list resulting in 429 valid entries associated with traffic signs, warning, safety, accident prevention, new driving laws, and intoxicated driver themes. Some entries included sets with multiple stamps so the total number of unique stamps, specialized pairs, or specialized souvenir sheets was 571. These stamps came from 119 different countries and spanned the years 1932-2023.

3.2 Data Preparation and Analysis

Some cells in the database had nonstandard entries, such as “N/A” – these entries were removed. Further, countries with multiple stamp issues in the same year on this topic were removed to avoid confounding effects. The decision was made to use the values within the database for ‘decrease in fatalities’, so negative numbers were indicative of increases in fatalities.

The authors employed several statistical methods to analyze the data. Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of the distribution for each year's data (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965). Given the data's non-normal distribution, the authors used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to compare fatality rates between years (Wilcoxon, 1945). Despite the non-normal distribution, we also conducted paired t-tests and one-way ANOVA to assess completeness and compare them with non-parametric results (Student, 1908; Fisher, 1925). To control for other factors, the authors performed a multiple regression analysis, including a dummy variable for developed/developing countries (Cohen et al., 2003). Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test was used to compare all pairs of means following the ANOVA (Tukey, 1949).

The authors used a paired t-test to compare fatality rates in the year of the stamp issue (Year 0) with rates one year after (Year 1) and two years after (Year 2) the stamp issue. This helped determine if there was a significant change in fatality rates following stamp issues.

3.3 Qualitative Analysis of Literature

A targeted literature review was conducted to understand the potential impacts of stamp issues on public awareness and behavior related to traffic safety. This included examining case studies, theoretical frameworks, and challenges in measuring the effectiveness of such interventions. The literature review followed the guidelines outlined by Petticrew and Roberts (2006). This method was chosen to synthesize existing research on using stamps as public awareness tools and their potential effects on behavior change.

3.4 Search Strategy

We searched databases, including Web of Science, Scopus, JSTOR, and Google Scholar, for relevant literature published between 1990 and 2023. The search terms included combinations of keywords such as "postage stamps," "philately," "traffic safety," "road safety," "public awareness," "behavior change," and "nudge theory." We also manually searched reference lists from identified articles to ensure comprehensive coverage.

Studies were included if they met the following criteria:

1. Focused on the use of postage stamps or related philatelic products for public awareness campaigns
2. Addressed issues related to traffic safety or similar public health concerns
3. Discussed the potential impact on public awareness or behavior change
4. Were peer-reviewed articles, books, or official reports published in English

3.5 Data Extraction and Analysis

We extracted data from the selected studies using a standardized form that captured information on study design, context, intervention details, outcomes, and critical findings. The extracted data were then analyzed using a thematic approach described by Braun and Clarke (2006). This involved identifying recurring themes and patterns across the literature related to the use and effectiveness of stamps in public awareness campaigns.

3.6 Quality Assessment

The quality of the included studies was assessed using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist for qualitative research (CASP, 2018). This tool evaluates various aspects of qualitative studies, including clarity of aims, methodology appropriateness, and data analysis rigor. While this qualitative analysis provides valuable insights into the potential of stamps as nudges in public administration, it is important to note its limitations. The review was restricted to English-language publications, potentially missing relevant studies in other languages. Additionally, the scarcity of empirical studies examining the impact of traffic safety stamps on behavior change limited our ability to draw definitive conclusions.

Given these limitations, the qualitative findings should be interpreted as complementary to the quantitative analysis, offering context and potential explanations for the observed results rather than providing direct evidence of effectiveness.

4. RESULTS

The data shows significant variability in the impact of traffic safety stamp issues on fatality rates. Some countries experienced notable decreases in fatalities following stamp issues, while others saw increases or no apparent effect. This inconsistency suggests that stamp issues alone may not be a reliable predictor of changes in traffic fatality rates.

There's no consistent pattern in the timing of effects. Some countries show immediate decreases in fatalities in the same year as the stamp issue, while others show delayed effects or fluctuating patterns over subsequent years. This variability makes it challenging to draw definitive conclusions about the direct impact of stamp issues on traffic safety.

Based on the fundamental statistical analysis, a paired t-test, we can draw the following main conclusions:

The paired t-tests did not reveal any statistically significant differences in fatality rates between the year of stamp issue and the following one or two years. This suggests that data does not support a conclusion that traffic safety stamp issues have a consistent, measurable impact on fatality rates.

The high p-values (0.4483 for Year 0 vs. Year 1 and 0.5604 for Year 0 vs. Year 2) indicate that the observed differences in fatality rates before and after stamp issues could be due to random variation rather than a systematic effect of the stamps.

4.1 Quantitative Findings

The quantitative analysis consistently showed no statistically significant short-term effects of traffic safety stamp issues on fatality rates. Key results include:

- Wilcoxon signed-rank test: No significant differences between Year 0 and Year 1 ($V = 382$, $p = 0.8807$) or Year 0 and Year 2 ($V = 385$, $p = 0.8711$)
- Paired t-tests: No significant differences between Year 0 and Year 1 ($t(38) = 0.7661$, $p = 0.4483$) or Year 0 and Year 2 ($t(38) = 0.5874$, $p = 0.5604$)
- Multiple regression: Low explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.006$, $F(3, 113) = 0.2321$, $p = 0.920$) with no significant predictors

Normality Tests

The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed that the fatality rate data for all three years were not normally distributed:

- Year 0: $W = 0.7105$, $p < 0.001$
- Year 1: $W = 0.6893$, $p < 0.001$
- Year 2: $W = 0.7246$, $p < 0.001$

These results indicate a significant departure from normality for all three years, justifying non-parametric tests for the primary analysis.

Non-parametric Tests

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed no statistically significant differences between:

- Year 0 and Year 1: $V = 382$, $p = 0.8807$
- Year 0 and Year 2: $V = 385$, $p = 0.8711$

These results suggest no significant changes in fatality rates in the years following stamp issues.

Parametric Tests

Despite the non-normal distribution, we conducted parametric tests for completeness:

Paired t-tests results:

- Year 0 vs Year 1: $t(38) = 0.7661$, $p = 0.4483$
- Year 0 vs Year 2: $t(38) = 0.5874$, $p = 0.5604$

One-way ANOVA results:

- $F(2, 114) = 0.2493$, $p = 0.7796$

- F-statistic: 0.2493

p-value: 0.7796 The high p-value suggests no statistically significant differences among the means of the three years' results, which align with the non-parametric tests.

Multiple Regression Analysis

A multiple regression model including a year of stamp issue and a dummy variable for developed/developing countries showed meager explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.006$, $F(3, 113) = 0.2321$, $p = 0.920$). None of the predictors were statistically significant:

- Year 1: $\beta = -4.4410$, $t(113) = -0.029$, $p = 0.977$
- Year 2: $\beta = -21.2474$, $t(113) = -0.140$, $p = 0.889$
- Developed country: $\beta = -82.1088$, $t(113) = -0.541$, $p = 0.589$

Tukey's HSD Test

Post-hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD test confirmed no significant differences between years. All pairwise comparisons showed p-values > 0.05 , confirming no significant differences between years.

- Year 0 vs Year 1: diff = 71.5138, $p = 0.8398$
- Year 0 vs Year 2: diff = 84.2382, $p = 0.7891$
- Year 1 vs Year 2: diff = 12.7244, $p = 0.9000$

5. DISCUSSION

It is worth noting that the World Health Organization had instituted the World Health Day in 2004, with the focus of reducing traffic fatalities, and official direction to increase awareness of the problem; one venue for such messaging appears was clearly stamps (Peden, Scurfield, Sleet, Mohan, & Hyder, 2004). Russia shows some of the largest decreases in fatalities, with significant drops in 2004, 2009, and 2016 following stamp issues. However, the scale of these changes (e.g., -5477 in 2009) suggests other factors may be at play. France shows an interesting pattern: fatalities increased in 2001, followed by a significant decrease in 2004 after stamp issues in those years. Some smaller countries like Kiribati and Tonga show no change (0) in fatalities, which could be due to their smaller population sizes or lower baseline fatality rates. The significant variations in fatality changes suggest that other factors beyond stamp issues likely influence traffic safety. These could include changes in traffic laws or enforcement; Economic factors affecting vehicle usage or road infrastructure investment; Improvements in vehicle safety technology; and Public awareness campaigns or educational initiatives.

Performing statistical tests allowed us to determine if the observed changes were statistically significant or merely due to random variation to make more substantial claims about the effectiveness of stamp issues.

The fatality data is not normally distributed, which is typical for real-world data, especially with small sample sizes. This non-normality justified the use of non-parametric tests. Both the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and the multiple regression analysis indicate no statistically significant changes in fatality rates following stamp issues up to two years after the

problem. The regression model has meager explanatory power (R-squared of 0.006), suggesting that the year of the stamp issue and the developed/developing country classification are not good predictors of changes in fatality rates. The low R-squared value and lack of significant predictors suggest that other factors not included in this analysis may be more important in determining changes in fatality rates.

While the data does not show a statistically significant impact of traffic safety stamp issues on fatality rates, this analysis should be considered preliminary. With a different set of data, it is possible that different results might be seen; however, this analysis does not show short-run results from stamp issues on behavior, which would result in a decrease in traffic accidents. Based on this analysis, though, we cannot conclude that traffic safety stamp issues significantly impact fatality rates in the short term (up to two years after the problem). The analysis is constrained by the small sample size, limited variables, short time frame, and simplified country classification. These limitations highlight the need for more comprehensive data collection and analysis in future research.

Qualitative Findings

The literature review revealed key themes regarding the potential of stamps as nudges:

1. Stamps offer a distinctive platform for social marketing due to their widespread reach and cultural significance (Brunn, 2001).
2. Awareness and Memory: Stamp designs can have a lasting impact on memory and perception (Brennan, 2018), suggesting the potential for enhancing the retention of safety messages.
3. Normative Influence: Stamps could activate safety norms by depicting desired behaviors, aligning with the theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Lapinski, 2015).
4. Emotional Appeal: Stamps' visual nature allows for emotional appeals, which have been effective in road safety campaigns (Delhomme et al., 2009).
5. Educational Potential: Stamps can serve as practical educational tools, particularly for younger audiences (Kirby, 2018).
6. Case Studies: Examples from countries like India and Sweden demonstrate how traffic safety stamps can generate media attention and complement broader safety initiatives (Gupta et al., 2021; Belin et al., 2012).
7. Integration: Phillips et al. (2011) note the difficulty in isolating the effects of specific media in road safety campaigns, suggesting that stamps may be most effective when integrated with broader safety initiatives.
8. Glenn (1983) demonstrated how postage stamps can effectively enhance social studies education by providing a tangible link to historical and cultural topics.

From a public administration standpoint, the lack of significant quantitative results raises essential questions

about resource allocation and policy effectiveness. As Moynihan (2008) argues, performance measurement and evidence-based decision-making are crucial in modern public administration. The discrepancy between quantitative and qualitative findings highlights the challenges of evaluating complex policy interventions. This underscores the need for more sophisticated evaluation methods in public administration, as advocated by Newcomer et al. (2015), to capture both tangible outcomes and intangible impacts of policy initiatives.

5.1 Stamps as Nudges in Public Administration

While the quantitative analysis did not show significant short-term effects on fatality rates, the qualitative findings suggest that stamps have potential as nudges in public administration. Their unique characteristics align with critical principles of nudge theory:

1. Salience: Stamps make safety messages visually salient in everyday life (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008).
2. Social Norms: Stamps can reinforce social norms regarding traffic safety by depicting safe behaviors (John et al., 2011).
3. Emotional Appeal: Stamps' visual appeal allows for emotional engagement, an essential aspect of effective nudges (Dolan et al., 2012).

However, the lack of measurable short-term impact on fatality rates highlights the challenges in implementing and evaluating nudge strategies in complex policy areas like traffic safety.

The quantitative analysis consistently showed no statistically significant short-term effects of traffic safety stamp issues on fatality rates. This lack of measurable impact in the two years following stamp issues suggests that if there is an effect, it's not detectable with the current dataset and methods.

However, qualitative research indicates that traffic safety stamps may impact public awareness and behavior. Their unique characteristics as a medium for social marketing and their ability to evoke emotional responses and activate social norms suggest they could shape attitudes toward road safety. Several factors may contribute to the discrepancy between the quantitative and qualitative findings. The quantitative analysis was limited to two years after the stamp issue, which may be insufficient to capture long-term behavioral changes. Note that the impact of cultural artifacts like stamps may take time to manifest in measurable outcomes. Further, traffic fatality rates are influenced by numerous factors beyond public awareness, including road infrastructure, vehicle safety technology, and traffic law enforcement (WHO, 2018). The regression analysis's low R^2 value (0.006) underscores the complexity of the factors influencing fatality rates.

Additionally, stamps may contribute to a broader culture of safety awareness that is not directly reflected in short-term fatality statistics. We are reminded by Phillips et al. (2011) that isolating the effects of specific media in road safety campaigns is inherently difficult. Concurrent safety

initiatives or socioeconomic changes may obscure the impact of stamp campaigns.

The findings of this study have significant implications for public administrators tasked with developing and implementing traffic safety policies. As Osborne (2006) notes, the New Public Governance paradigm emphasizes the importance of networks and partnerships in addressing complex social issues. In this context, stamp-based interventions are part of a broader network of policy tools and stakeholder engagements to improve traffic safety. However, the limited quantitative impact observed in this study suggests that public administrators should consider stamp campaigns complementary to, rather than replacements for, more direct interventions such as infrastructure improvements or law enforcement efforts (Wegman et al., 2015).

Any campaign needs to be carefully crafted to avoid producing an unintended negative response. Attempts to influence behavior—especially through public messaging—can at times produce the opposite of the intended effect. For example, public service announcements can backfire and instead of persuading people to adopt a desired behavior or belief, these messages may reinforce the very attitudes or actions they are meant to change. This phenomenon occurs because the unconscious mind processes information in complex ways, often filtering messages through existing biases and social identities. As an example, an anti-smoking campaign may inadvertently make the targeted behavior or attitude more salient, leading individuals to double down on their existing views (Mlodinow, 2012). This could be why traffic safety related stamps have not had the intended impact that was hoped by the issuing government entity.

5.2 Alternative Strategies in the Digital Age

As postal usage declines, alternative strategies for nudging behavior in public administration could include leveraging social media, mobile apps, and other digital platforms to deliver targeted messages and nudges (Weinmann et al., 2016). Incorporating nudges into urban design and smart city initiatives, such as road layouts that naturally encourage slower driving, might be a part of smart infrastructure worth investigation and investment (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). Gamification has shown promise, and using game-like elements in non-game contexts to encourage desired behaviors may prove useful (Deterding et al., 2011). Utilizing big data and AI to deliver customized nudges through various digital channels can allow for message personalization (Benartzi et al., 2017); this would move well beyond the effectiveness of stamps. Implementing AR applications that can provide real-time safety nudges in traffic environments (Meola et al., 2017). Technology has a role to play - Recent studies have shown the effectiveness of smartphone apps in promoting road safety behaviors (Zhang et al., 2019). These strategies could offer more dynamic, personalized, and measurable alternatives to traditional stamp-based nudges.

5.3 Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered. The quantitative analysis was limited to two years post-stamp issue, potentially missing long-term effects. The regression analysis included only a few variables, potentially omitting important factors influencing traffic fatalities. Country-level data may obscure regional variations in the impact of stamp issues. The study design did not include a control group of countries that did not issue traffic safety stamps. The quantitative analysis did not account for changes in traffic laws, economic conditions, or other safety initiatives concurrent with stamp issues.

It is crucial to note that this analysis has several limitations, including a small sample size, lack of control for other variables, and potential non-normality of the data. These factors could be masking real effects or leading to misleading conclusions.

The lack of population data makes it difficult to contextualize the changes in fatality rates relative to each country's size. Without additional control variables, isolating the effect of stamp issues from other potential factors influencing traffic safety is challenging. The inconsistency in available data (e.g., N/A values for some years) limits the completeness of the analysis.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

While this quantitative analysis did not demonstrate a significant short-term impact of traffic safety stamp issues on fatality rates, this is a finding, because there remains a reliance on such media for public messaging. The results here suggest that such messaging does not, at least over the short term, yield a result a statistically significant result.

This noted, qualitative research suggests the potential for stamps and related philatelic products to contribute to public awareness and long-term behavioral change. As nudges in public administration, stamps offer unique advantages in reach, cultural significance, and ability to reinforce social norms.

However, public administrators should consider a multi-faceted approach that combines traditional methods like stamps with emerging digital strategies as postal usage declines. Future research and policy initiatives should focus on extending the analysis timeframe to capture the potential delayed effects of stamp-based nudges on traffic safety outcomes. It would be worthwhile to investigate the role of stamp issues within broader traffic safety campaigns that incorporate both traditional and digital nudges. As stamp-based approaches may be limited, it would be worthwhile to consider developing digital alternatives to stamp-based nudges, considering their potential for more personalized and measurable interventions. Diverse cultural contexts may explain differing results: future research might examine how the effectiveness of various nudge strategies may vary across different cultural contexts.

Consistent with past behavioral public administration research, it is valid to address the ethical implications of nudge strategies in public administration, particularly as they become more personalized and data-driven. Experts in public health, psychology, and media studies could be engaged to develop more effective stamp campaigns, leveraging insights from various disciplines as demonstrated in the work of on-road safety communication campaigns.

By understanding the strengths and limitations of various nudge strategies, including traditional methods like stamps and emerging digital approaches, public administrators can develop more effective, ethical, and adaptable interventions to promote public welfare in areas such as traffic safety. Future research should focus on creating more sophisticated methods for evaluating the impact of these small but potentially influential public health interventions. By better understanding how traffic safety stamps may influence public awareness and behavior, we can optimize their use as part of comprehensive road safety strategies.

Considering public administration, this study underscores the importance of evidence-based policymaking and the need for innovative approaches to public engagement. Bryson et al. (2014) argue that creating public value often requires leveraging multiple strategies and engaging diverse stakeholders. While stamp-based nudges may not show immediate quantitative impacts, their potential to contribute to long-term cultural shifts aligns with the strategic approach to public administration advocated by Moore (1995). Public administrators should consider how stamp campaigns and other nudge strategies can be integrated into comprehensive approaches to traffic safety and other policy domains. This may involve developing new metrics for evaluating policy effectiveness that capture both short-term outcomes and long-term societal impacts.

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Photo A Examples of Traffic Safety Stamps

